

Cold Sintering: A Novel Strategy for Densifying Minerals

N. Sibi, G. Subodh*

Department of Physics, University of Kerala, Thiruvananthapuram-695 581, India

*Corresponding author: Tel: 91-4712308920; E- Mail: gsubodh@gmail.com

Abstract

Cold Sintering (CSP) is a new energy efficient low temperature sintering technique using alkaline or acidic solvents to densify ceramic materials by simultaneously applying temperature (below 300 °C) and pressure (in MPa range) [1]. The aqueous environment between the ceramic particles enhances densification by a dissolution precipitation process. Since CSP is performed at very low temperatures, the problems due to high temperature sintering such as heat expansion, cracking or dimensional changes of the pellets can be avoided. It has a great potential in integration of ceramics and polymers, silver electrode integration in LTCC, ceramic composites for magnetodielectric applications etc. In the present study, natural garnet mineral, which decomposes above 600 °C was densified using CSP and the properties were studied. The composites of the garnet with different volume fractions of NaCl (dielectric) and V₂O₅ (conducting) were fabricated using water as the solvent. A pressure of 450 MPa and temperature of 120°C - 200°C was applied for 50 minutes. The composites showed a density in the range of 80 % - 95 %. Crystallographic, microstructural and electrical properties of the composites were studied. For, 0.5 garnet – 0.5 NaCl, dielectric constant (ϵ_r) = 8.2 & $\tan \delta = 0.02$ at $f = 10$ GHz and for 0.5 garnet-0.5 V₂O₅, $\epsilon_r = 240$, $\tan \delta = 1.33$ & conductivity (σ) = 8.02×10^{-3} S/m at $f = 1$ MHz.

Figure: Microstructure of (1-x) garnet/x NaCl composites (a) x = 0.1 (b) x = 0.3 (c) x = 0.5

Keywords: Cold sintering, Garnet mineral, Microstructure, Electric properties

References

1. J Guo et al, Angew. Chem., 128(2016) 11629.